

ATTITUDE TOWARDS CONTINUOUS AND COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: The study was conducted to find out attitude towards CCE among high school students of Kadayanallur Taluk. This study adopted a descriptive survey design due to the implicit nature of the study. Simple random sampling method was adopted by selecting 300 high school students from schools of Kadayanallur Taluk. A self-made questionnaire called Attitude towards CCE Scale constructed and validated by Dr. N. Subramanian and Mrs. M. Kalaiselvi was used to find out the level of Attitude. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and F-test. It was concluded that there is insignificant difference among government, aided and self-financed high school students attitude towards CCE.

Index Terms: CCE, High school students, F-test, government, self-financed, aided.(keywords)

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaluation forms an integral part of teaching-learning process. Continuous evaluation of learners achievement is carried out periodically during the teaching – learning process to judge if the competency has been mastered by the learner. Evaluation is commonly done only in the cognitive areas of learning such as knowledge and understanding and some basic skills. Evaluation of non-cognitive areas of learning such as values, interests, attitudes, habits, etc. is hardly attempted. Effective evaluation procedures need to be employed so as to measure both cognitive and non-cognitive learning outcomes. Emphasis should not be on measurement of learners learning alone but for improvement of their achievement on a regular basis. If some ‘slow’ learners not ready to develop or learn competency completely, their weakness need to be diagnosed and the hard spots of learning identified and followed by appropriate remedial programme. Evaluation therefore should be continuous and comprehensive for evaluating learners’ achievement in both cognitive and non-cognitive areas on a regular basis for their scholastic and non scholastic growth, by the teacher through periodical tests by employing variety of tools, techniques and regular feedback. The final grade a learner receives in a course or session is not based on a single final annual examination, but takes into account the results of the evaluation through the session[2]. The continuous and comprehensive evaluation will provide space to understand learners’ ability with reference to their meta-cognitive abilities associated with social problems, issues and concerns. There are three terms involved in the frame work of continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Continuous: Education is a continuous process. So, the progress of the students should be evaluated and frequently. Comprehensive: The term ‘comprehensive’ means to both scholastic and non-scholastic areas of students. Therefore, the role of teacher is to build up the cognitive as well as non-cognitive abilities. Evaluation: Evaluation is the process of knowing up to what extent the desired changes have taken place in the students [1]. In contemporary world, Students’ attitude is considered more important than their experiences and academic preparation. A positive attitude towards CCE is a key to success and progress in their academic achievement. This study explored the students’ attitude towards CCE [4].

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method among high school students with regard to type of school.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among boys’, girls’ and co-education school high school students in their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

III. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference among boys’, girls’ and co-education school high school students in their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design due to the implicit nature of the study. Simple random sampling method was adopted by selecting 300 high school students from schools of Kadayanallur Taluk. A self-made questionnaire called Attitude towards CCE Scale constructed and validated by Dr. N. Subramanian and Mrs. M. Kalaiselvi was used to find out the level of Attitude. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and F-test.

V. ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive analysis of data

Objective: To find out the level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method among high school students with regard to type of school.

Table – 1 Level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method among high school students with regard to type of school

Type of school	Low		Moderate		High	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Government	0	0	91	100	0	0
Aided	0	0	89	100	0	0
Self - Financed	1	0.8	117	97.5	2	1.7

It is inferred from the above table that 100% of government high school students have moderate level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method. 100% of aided high school students have moderate level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method. 0.8% of the self-financed high school students have low, 97.5% of them have moderate and 1.7% of them have high level of attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

Inferential analysis of data

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among government, aided and self-financed high school students in their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

Table 2 F-test showing the significant difference among government, aided and self-financed school high school students in their attitude towards CCE method

Variable	Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' value	Remarks at 5% level
Attitude towards CCE	Between	4999.437	2	2499.719	0.865	NS*
	Within	858052.149	297	2889.064		
	Total	863051.587	299			

(* Not significant at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated 'f' value (0.865) is less than the table value (3.00) for df (2,297) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference among government, aided and self-financed school high school students in their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

VI. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- The descriptive analysis of data revealed that more than 97% of government, government aided and self-financed high school students have moderate level of attitude towards CCE.
- And also the results of F-test in inferential analysis exposed that there is no significant difference among government, aided and self-financed high school students in their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation method.

VII. CONCLUSION

In the present study, the investigator found from descriptive analysis that most of the high school students have moderate level of attitude towards CCE and also found from inferential analysis that the government, aided and self-financed high school students have lack of attitude towards CCE. Student and teacher roles describe the relationship of these individuals to one another and to the content, materials, and activities. In student-centered classrooms, students take a much more active role: they decide what activities to do and when, and they consult with the teacher to identify reasonable and worthwhile activities and discuss plans for completing them. In such cases, the teacher acts as a supervisor or resource, advising students about their choices, directing them to relevant materials, and providing feedback on progress[5]. In today's student centered teaching learning process at high school level, the CCE is also one part of it. So before implementation of CCE in schools, the teachers fully elucidated the nature of CCE and its implication their students. It is, therefore, important and imperative for stakeholders of school education to develop positive attitude towards CCE and make evaluation process interesting and appealing to students in order to help them develop a positive attitude towards it.

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